

Associated Data Stewards as Means to Broaden Domain-Specific Expertise

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Network – Goals

FOR USERS

- Create a larger pool of entry points for questions in the agricultural research domain
- Enlarge portfolio of services offered
 - Find better fitting solutions in term of topics offered, locations covered etc.

FOR HELPDESKS

- Access to infrastructures (e.g. repositories)
- Learn from each other

Introducing the (tr)actors:

Data Management Support @SLU

Services:

- Communication
- Data curation & publishing
- Data storage
- DMPs
- Education & outreach
- Environmental monitoring and assessment
- Law
- Long term preservation

FAIRagro @ZALF

The FAIRagro Helpdesk

Elena

Plant Breeding
Data management plan (DMP)
MIAPPE
...

Lucia

Farming 4.0
Field robotics
Visualization
...

Florian

Big Geodata
Curation and metadata
Web services and SDI
Quality and provenance
...

Coordination
NFDI networking
Data Science
...

Marcus

Data Publication
Long term experiments
DOI
Metadata
...

Wahib

Law & Ethics
Intellectual property
Copyright and licensing
Data privacy
...

Lea

Associated
Data
Stewards

U N I K A S S E L
V E R S I T Ä T

Link to our
FAIRagro Training
Measure

FAIRagro

WDCC @WUR

A strategic hub for data management support

Library RDM Support

- DMP reviews
- Data publishing and Archiving
- Guidance
- Training
- Question hub
- Community management data stewards
- Collaboration Security/Privacy/Legal/IT

Science Group RDM Support

- Guidance
- Community management data stewards
- Maturity assessment and monitoring
- Collaboration Security/Privacy/Legal

Network - Proposed Structure & Workflow

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"Remember that request you forwarded to us? – We were able to find a fitting repository and the customer is happy."

"It's not our main focus but if you like, SLU can answer this for you – can I forward your request to them?"

A common denominator: our repositories

BonaRes Repository
for soil and
agricultural data

... and a European [LTE map](#)

Search geographical data

Filters

- Subject
- Data format / data structure
- Language
- Collection
- Research principal
- Accessibility level
- Access to data

Extended filters

List View

Results in list (2915)

Accessibility levels for data

- = Access to data through SND
- = Access to data through an external actor
- = Data are freely accessible
- = Access to data is restricted or accessible by request

In the national SND research data catalogue, you can search for research data from a variety of research disciplines. Some data can be downloaded in the catalogue entry, whereas others are accessible by request. There are also data that are only described in the catalogue and accessible through another portal/party.

Refine your search using the filter function.

If you are looking for data with geographical information, you can search using the map view.

Search in SND's Catalogue **SEARCH**

[SND research data catalogue](#) – various fields including agriculture

FAIRagro

A common denominator: our repositories

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

Contact & Help

Home Profiles Research units Research output **Datasets** Press/Media Activities Projects Prizes

Find research data

Advanced search

Wageningen Research Data – including Plant Sciences

Search in all content

Filters for Datasets

Publication Year

- 2024 (58)
- 2023 (128)
- 2022 (124)
- 2021 (156)
- 2020 (144)

Show more >

Person

SELECTED FILTERS CLEAR ALL

RESEARCH UNITS

Department of Plant Sciences x

1 - 25 out of 1,425 results

Start date (descending) >

Export search results

Data from: Drought mitigates negative effects of natural microbiomes in grasses

Rallo, P. (Creator), Bakx-Schotman, T. (Creator), Kammenga, J. (Creator), van der Putten, W. (Creator), Hannula, S. E. (Creator) & Verhoeven, K. J. F. (Creator), Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW), 10 May 2024

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Dataset

FAIRagro

How to join the network

Get in contact with:

dataservice@fairagro.net

(FAIRagro Helpdesk)

dms@slu.se (SLU Data
Management Support)

[contact WDCC](#)

... or come talk to us after the
presentation

